

SEMANTICS OF TERMS IN BILINGUAL LINGUISTIC DICTIONARIES

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the process of semantics of terms in bilingual and linguistic dictionaries. The main focus is on the analysis of denotative and functional meanings of terms, their role in conveying the exact meaning and systematizing scientific concepts. The principles and methods of semanticization, including translation of equivalents, explanatory translation, contextual interpretation, and cognitive approach, are considered. Particular attention is paid to the lack of connotative meanings in linguistic dictionaries and their significance in bilingual dictionaries for a wide audience. The article also analyzes examples from different dictionaries that demonstrate similarities and differences in approaches to the semantics of terms. The work emphasizes the importance of semantics as a key tool for creating accurate and informative dictionaries.

Key words: semantics, denotative, connotative, functional meanings, equivalents, linguistic dictionaries, contextual interpretation.

Semantization is an important concept in lexicography and translation theory. In a broad sense, semanticization refers to the process of explaining the meanings of a word, their semantic types, that is, denotative, connotative and functional meanings, polysemy, homonymy, synonymy and antonymic meanings, in particular, cultural connotations and contextual features. The primary goal of semanticization is not only to convey the meaning of a word clearly, but also to adapt it to the syntactic, communicative, and cultural contexts of another language being translated.

Semantization is related to the use of words. As noted by the renowned Russian linguist B.Yu. Norman, "In lexical semantics, there are possibilities for using a word in speech," that is, the meaning of a word is fully reflected in its dynamic use in real speech. Lexical semantics studies the meaning of a word, how it is used in different contexts and how it gives meaning. According to B. Yu Norman, the meaning of a word is not constant, it can change depending on how the word is used in context and purpose, that is, different aspects of the meaning of the word depend on how it is used in the process of communication. For example, contextual use (the meaning of a word can be different in different contexts); polysemy (a single word can have several meanings, and this enriches its speech activity) or functional role (a word can be used in speech as a noun, verb, or adjective, which determines its meaning and function). Therefore, the meaning of a word is not limited to vocabulary or grammatical concepts; it constantly changes depending on its practical application. Lexical semantics emphasizes the need to study not only the meanings of words, but also how they are used in various situations.

G.A. Zolotova, one of the renowned linguists in Russian linguistics, supports the above-mentioned approach and expresses the following opinion: "Nouns in different groups exhibit themselves syntactically differently, which largely depends on their meaning." The semantic properties of these words and their syntactic use demonstrate their interconnectedness. The meaning of a word is the main factor that determines its grammatical and syntactic function. The direct (denotative) meaning of a word determines the role it plays in a sentence. The

meaning of a word depends on the syntactic structure, and in the context it performs different functions. For example, in a lexical syntactic connection, the meaning of a word affects how it relates to other words. If we look at the grammatical functions, the syntactic role of the word is manifested in various sentence types along with its meaning. This opinion points to the need for a deeper reflection of the semantic and syntactic use of words in dictionaries. Therefore, in the process of semanticization, the syntactic functions of the word must also be explained. The opinion of the linguist G.A. Zolotova indicates the need for a deeper study of the lexical and syntactic aspects of the semantics process. These dictionaries serve as an important scientific basis for providing more detailed information about the correct interpretation of words and their use.

These opinions also confirm the continuous connection between the semantic diversity of the word and its syntactic use. Lexical units in speech are not limited only to their denotative meaning, but also have the ability to create meaning in different contexts through their functional functions.

This once again confirms the complexity of the semantic process. Semanticization serves to create a complete picture of a word by studying not only its main meaning, but also its contextual, pragmatic and cultural aspects. Therefore, the theory of semanticization appears as a broad concept that includes the polysemy of the word, its possibilities of use and syntactic place. Semanticization is also known as a complex process based on the multifaceted nature of lexical units. It includes not only the clear and direct meaning of the word, but also its features of use in speech, cultural and emotional connections. This multifaceted nature of semanticization makes it the main concept in linguistics and lexicography. In the semantic system of language, each word can have several meanings, and these meanings are reflected in the following aspects. For example, the word "green" is used in different meanings, based on the Russian-Karakalpak dictionary compiled by A. Turabaev, K. Seitova, K. Koshanov, B. Khoshanov, K. Saparov and Z. Turabaeva, published in 2010. Explaining its denotative and connotative meanings better reveals the use of this word in vocabulary and context.

1. Denotative meaning is the direct, object-oriented meaning of a word. This is the primary and primary meaning of the word and directly indicates an object or event in the real world.

For example, in the dictionary, the first meaning given to the word "green" is "green, blue; The color is presented in the form of "green."

2. Connotative meaning - emotional, cultural and metaphorical types of words. Connotative meaning adds layers of additional meaning to the word and strengthens its emotional impact. The way the word is perceived can change depending on the cultural environment.

For example, in the aforementioned dictionary, the word "green" has the second meaning "green, blue." in the third sense "young".

3. Functional meaning - expresses the grammatical or syntactic role of a word. This explains the function of the word in the sentence, that is, it belongs to one of the noun, adjective, verb or other grammatical forms.

For example, in the aforementioned Russian-Karakalpak dictionary, the word "green" serves as an adjective in the sentence, its gender and plural forms are shown: -aya, -oye, -iye. Also, the abbreviated form: -len, -lena, -lena is given.

If we generalize the presented data, the word "green" broadly reflects denotative and functional meanings in bilingual dictionaries, but the connotative meaning is reflected less. In linguistic dictionaries, attention is mainly paid to functional and technical aspects, connotative meanings are almost neglected. Due to the fact that the tasks and directions of these dictionaries are different, each dictionary provides information to its users in an appropriate way. Joint analysis of denotative, connotative, and functional meanings allows for a deeper understanding of different aspects of words through dictionaries.

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